

Wages theory: A new insight regarding interest rate and the Bonds Market

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Abstract

The theory of wages states that interest rates have an effect on the change of such a variable, classicals likewise had never pretended that workers have come to efficiency regarding their beloved professions and how the equilibrium between interest rate and risk in the Stock Market is needed for regressing the wage with respect to interest rate and volatility, we give a formal definition of interest rate which fits with the fact companies invite their employees to invest their current wages in a zero-coupon bond with a specific choice regarding return.

Afterward, we define unions and companies relation mindfully and recall the fact involuntary unemployment is a fact in the Market due to John Maynard Keynes' consciousness, we did some theoretical pricing of Vanilla Options that hopefully would give a sense to our precious model.

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1 Introduction

Hypothesis: We do suppose the Stock Market is fractional, we use the bifractional motion $B^{H,K}$, the use of two dimensions to model volatility goes intuitively in accordance with the assumption that the long memory of volatility has two sides, one accomplished with respect to this memory itself and another which mentions at which extent the history of variations is recalled by volatility, past investments in the Stock Market are in fact leading the Stock Market to remind past memory.

Definition: We define wages change with respect to interest rate in our guise reflecting on the behavior of interest rate, let's give this formal definition that we suppose true for our analysis, it's a definition that holds true in a large sens:

The change of wages with respect to interest rate change is the rate that would guarantee this equality:

$$\frac{dw_t}{dr_t} = \begin{cases} -(r_t - r_{t-1})w_{t-1} & \text{if } r_t - r_{t-1} \geq 0 \\ (r_t - r_{t-1})w_{t-1} & \text{if } r_t - r_{t-1} \leq 0 \end{cases}$$

We suppose that this equilibrium has a sense for predicting the path of wages, in the welfare economics interest rate had been defined as the mediator between investments and savings, in this study we suppose wages are all invested in a zero-coupon bond with a rate of return equal to $(r_T - r_t)^2$. Such a supposition goes in considering that workers are delicate gamblers that have an aversion for risk, we might as well give a name to such a precious discovery in quantitative economics. If workers are willing to preserve their bonds until the maturity they would earn $w_T = w_t + (r_T - r_t)^2 w_t$ which shows how some companies would propose such a deal with employees, pay them w_t at time t then invite them to invest their money in short maturity zero-coupon bonds with this rate, the choice of the rate of return is not arbitrary, in economics the square of a quantity is understood as its equivalent in \mathcal{R}^2 , we do believe though that our choice doesn't fold a bit when it is made of fruitful theory.

In the case interest rate augments from r_t into r_T those bonds offer a negative return, companies invest wages on behalf of workers at time t , at time T if interest rates have augmented the bill is negative for companies they take less than their invested money which is $w_t(1 - (r_T - r_t)^2)$, it is arguably a systematic economical law, when interest rate descends companies retreat their savings $w_t + (r_T - r_t)^2 w_t$ to pay workers thus impoverishing Banks after they had been favoured due to interest rate augmentation creating a balance in the accounting of Banks.

Afterward we discussed welfare economics by making an exact pricing of Options and dealing with keynesian definition of involuntary unemployment which we had shown very consistent with our model and under the simplifications we made about workers and employees.

Card, David and Alan B. Krueger (1995) have discussed the minimum wage policies and invented such a novelty toward explaining that higher minimum wages decreases professions for low-wage employees, this equilibrium is held accountable after testing economic data.

Akerlof, G.A., Katz, L.F. (1990) have studied the labour market distortions closely when they showed with persistence that the absence of up-front bonds is responsible for the

difference between bonding models and efficiency wage models.

Fehr, Ernst, and Armin Falk. (1999) have shown that workers underbidding is so common when wrkers can't yet quit the Market if their wages are very low.

2 Model

Wages are normally set by unions and companies, the unions are another part of the job, that's all we can see in time of mispricing, let's write our model as the following

$$w_t = w_t^* + g(r_t, h_t)$$

where w^* is the efficient level of wages when the cost of production is all reflected in wages, the function g accounts for anomalies in the labour market due to interest rate r and volatility of the stock market h . We would suppose that this volatility is fractional for some kind of commodities.

The Figarch model is specified as mean reverting equation using the following formula as a starting point:

$$\Phi(L)(1-L)^d(\ln\sigma_t^2 - \omega) = \Psi(L)g(z_{t-1})$$

Where ω is the mean variance and $\Phi(L)$ and $\Psi(L)$ are polynomials in the lag operator, $\Phi(L) = (1 - \Phi_1 L) \times \dots (1 - \Phi_p L)$ and $\Psi(L) = (1 - \Psi_1 L) \times \dots (1 - \Psi_p L)$ and $(1 - L)^d$ is the fractional difference operator defined by its binomial expansion:

$$(1 - L)^d = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(i-d)}{\Gamma(-d)\Gamma(i+1)} L^i$$

The function g above is allowed to include the effect past returns has on the current volatility and has the following form:

$$g(z_t) = \theta z_t + \gamma(|z_t| - E|z_t|)$$

where $z_t = \frac{\epsilon_t}{\sigma_t}$ is the normalized innovation

we take into consideration the character volatility always shows as a mean reverting function tending to converge to a constant value and we should define it again as the following:

$$h_t = (1 - L)^d(\ln\sigma_t^2 - \omega)$$

It is then convenient to write the FIGARCH(1,d,1) model as:

$$h_t = (1 - L)^d(\ln\sigma_t^2 - \omega) = \Phi_1 h_{t-1} + g(z_{t-1}) + \Psi_1 g(z_{t-2})$$

3 Wages: A martingale approach

Hypothesis: Suppose wages are reflecting all the fundamental information at time $t = 0$, arguably this leads to

$$\begin{aligned} g(r_0, h_0) &= 0 \\ w_0 &= w_0^* \end{aligned}$$

Let's afterward consider the space of probability $(\Omega, H, \mathcal{L}_t)$ where $\mathcal{L}_t = \sigma(r_t, h_t)$, our inability to forecast Future wages makes us allowed to consider that wages are martingales under the the universe H . Let's write it as the following

$$E^H[\bar{w}_T/\mathcal{L}_t] = \bar{w}_t$$

Where $\bar{w}_T = \exp(-\int_t^T r_s ds)w_t$.

On the other hand let's consider the space of probability $(\Omega, P, \mathcal{F}_t)$ where $\mathcal{F}_t = \sigma(r_t)$, the change of interest rate influences wages as the following

$$\frac{dw_t}{dr_t} = \begin{cases} -(r_t - r_{t-1})w_{t-1} & \text{if } r_t - r_{t-1} \geq 0 \\ (r_t - r_{t-1})w_{t-1} & \text{if } r_t - r_{t-1} \leq 0 \end{cases}$$

If we do have the chance of interest rate increasing or decreasing with the same influence on wages, arguably if

$$P(w_T = w_t - (r_T - r_t)^2 w_t) = P(w_T = w_t + (r_T - r_t)^2 w_t) = \frac{1}{2}$$

We will be showing that wages are also martingales under the subjective probability P if interest rate is null

$$\begin{aligned} E^P[\bar{w}_T/\mathcal{F}_t] &= E^P[\exp(-\int_t^T r_s ds)w_T/\mathcal{F}_t] \\ &= \frac{1}{2}E^P[\exp(-\int_t^T r_s ds)((w_t - (r_T - r_t)^2 w_t) + (w_t + (r_T - r_t)^2 w_t))/\mathcal{F}_t] \\ &= \bar{w}_t \end{aligned}$$

If we do have

$$\begin{aligned} P(w_T = w_t - (r_T - r_t)^2 w_t) &= \alpha \\ P(w_T = w_t + (r_T - r_t)^2 w_t) &= 1 - \alpha \end{aligned}$$

We would investigate on the right condition that makes wages a martingale under the subjective probability P .

We have the following

$$\begin{aligned} E^P[\bar{w}_T/\mathcal{F}_t] &= E^P[\exp(-\int_t^T r_s ds)\alpha((w_t - (r_T - r_t)^2 w_t) + (1 - \alpha)(w_t + (r_T - r_t)^2 w_t))/\mathcal{F}_t] \\ &= E^P[(w_t + (r_T - r_t)^2 w_t) - 2\alpha(r_T - r_t)^2 w_t/\mathcal{F}_t] \end{aligned}$$

$(w_t)_{t \geq 0}$ is a Martingale under the subjective probability P if

$$(r_T - r_t)^2 - 2\alpha(r_T - r_t)^2 = 0$$

Which means

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{2}$$

Which ends our equivalence, we say that wages are a martingale under the subjective probability P under a null interest rate if and only if $\alpha = \frac{1}{2}$

Which means that under our Hypothesis that wages inefficiency is due to interest rate wages are difficult to predict under a low interest rate, the authorities can't predict wages trend if the interest rate behaves as a brownien motion, let's write interest rates and volatility as the following

$$\begin{aligned} dr_t &= \beta dB_t \\ dh_t &= (a - bh_t)dt + \gamma dB_t^{H,K} \end{aligned}$$

Where B is a classical brownien motion and $B^{H,K}$ is a bifractional brownien motion accounting for the long memory of the Stock market.

We would be investigating on the level of risk in the stock market that corresponds to wages unpredictability, we have the following

$$dg(r_t, h_t) = \frac{dg}{dr_t} \beta dB_t + \frac{dg}{dh_t} (a - bh_t)dt + \frac{dg}{dh_t} \gamma dB_t^{H,K} + \left(\frac{1}{2} \frac{d^2 g}{dr_t^2} + HK \frac{d^2 g}{dh_t^2} t^{2HK-1} \right) dt$$

Wages are Martingales if we have

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma &= 0 \\ \frac{dg}{dh_t} (a - bh_t) + \frac{1}{2} \frac{d^2 g}{dr_t^2} + HK \frac{d^2 g}{dh_t^2} t^{2HK-1} &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

If we should propose a solution for g as an affine function of interest rate and variance as the following

$$g(r_t, h_t) = -A(t, T)r_t + B(t, T)h_t$$

Where $A(t, T) \geq 0$

We would have either $B(t, T) = 0$ or $h_t = \frac{a}{b}$, arguably wages are martingale if their change is independent from the volatility of the Stock market which is absurd as a restriction, which means using the FIGARCH HYPOTHESIS GOVERNING VOLATILITY that the level of risk that delivers fair wages is

$$h_t = \frac{g(z_{t-1}) + \Psi g(z_{t-2})}{1 - \Phi} = \frac{a}{b}$$

Our vocation is to create some equilibrium between unions and companies, we suppose *à priori* that companies have more chance decreasing wages as a wish to maximize their profit, we would try to determine how much of money the firms must take from employer's wage which make it however possible to restore this amount of money again due to the unions pressure, this equilibrium holds all things are being equal as the following

$$E[w_T + Y/\mathcal{F}_t] = E[w_{T-1} - Y/\mathcal{F}_t]$$

With Y is a random variable accounting for the magnitude of expenditures the state omits or adds depending on the request that should prime, unions or companies, this equilibrium holds for consecutive instants, this would lead to the following

$$E[Y/\mathcal{F}_t] = \frac{1}{2}E[-C_{T-1,T}/\mathcal{F}_t]$$

With $C_{T-1,T} = w_T^* - w_{T-1}^*$ is the cost of productions between two consecutive periods $T - 1$ and T ; We could be expecting the Future wages using capital and the interest rate as the following

$$E^P[w_T/\mathcal{F}_t] = -2py - E[\exp(\int_t^T r_s ds)/\mathcal{F}_t]k_t$$

Where $C_{T-1,T} = w_T + k_T$ with k is the capital induced for building factories and $p = P(Y = y)$.

Our choice of a bifractional brownien motion for the volatility as an argument for the double memory that is either sticky for wages to move downward and a sloppy interest rate decreasing because of unions, we could have used only a fractional brownien motion, our argument is the bidimensional backround that makes short rates and volatility two factors leading to wages predictibility or the opposite.

Let's propose this function for the variations of the Spot price

$$S_t = f(h_t, r_t)$$

We wish to represent the Stock Market as a riskless market in which case we believe that even though the return of the Stocks is equal to the risk free rate, there are cases

when the premium risk gets above the loanable fund market, for this reason i believe that volatility as a matter of fact changes the course of events, how really the market is riskier or a detertiministic machine is relaxed in the following representation of the Stock market

$$\begin{aligned} S_t &= S_{t-1} \exp\left(\int_{t-1}^t r_s ds + bh_t\right) \\ &= S_{t-1} \exp(r_{t-1} + r_t + bh_t) \end{aligned}$$

With the Stock Market as martingale we have found this differential equation for our model

$$\frac{df}{dh}(a - bh_t) + HK \frac{d^2 f}{dh^2} t^{2HK-1} = \frac{-1}{2} \frac{d^2 f}{dr^2}$$

As the Stock market behaves as a martingale we would have the following

$$b(a - bh_t) + HK b^2 t^{2HK-1} = \frac{-1}{8}$$

That would lead to the following restriction for interest rate

$$\frac{b}{2}(r_t - r_{t-1}) = ba + HK t^{2HK-1} b^2 + \frac{1}{8}$$

We would use the last equilibrium of interest rate to price Vanilla Options under absence of arbitrage.

The price of a Vanilla Option with a strike K is

$$C_t = E[(S_T - K)^+ \exp(-\int_t^T r_s ds) / \mathcal{F}_t]$$

On the other hand

$$E[S_T \exp(-\int_t^T r_s ds) \mathbb{1}_{S_T \geq K} / \mathcal{F}_t] = E[S_T \exp(\frac{1}{n+1} \sum_{i=t}^T r_i) \mathbb{1}_{S_T \geq K} / \mathcal{F}_t]$$

On the other hand

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=t}^T r_i &= \sum_{i=t}^T r_{i-1} + H(i) \\ &= \sum_{i=t}^T r_{i-n} + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} H(i-j) \end{aligned}$$

With $H(i) = 2a + 2HKbi^{2HK-1} + \frac{1}{8}$

Which means

$$E[S_T \exp(-\int_t^T r_s ds) \mathbb{1}_{S_T \geq K} / \mathcal{F}_t] = \exp(-\frac{1}{n+1} \sum_{i=t}^T r_{i-n} + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} H(i-j)) E[S_T \mathbb{1}_{S_T \geq K} / \mathcal{F}_t]$$

We then have

$$\begin{aligned} E[S_T \mathbb{1}_{S_T \geq K} / \mathcal{F}_t] &= E[S_{T-3} \exp(\frac{1}{2}(r_T + r_{T-3}) + r_{T-1} + r_{T-2} + b(h_T + h_{T-1} + h_{T-2})) \mathbb{1}_{S_T \geq K} / \mathcal{F}_t] \\ &= S_t \exp(\frac{1}{2}r_t) E[\exp(\frac{1}{2}r_T + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \frac{T-i}{2} + b \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} h_{T-i}) \mathbb{1}_{S_T \geq K} / \mathcal{F}_t] \end{aligned}$$

After pricing Vanilla option using the underlying stock market, we do have interest in real prices too, our aim is to justify the Keynesian consideration that involuntary unemployment exists because of companies refusal to hire more employers alongside their wish to produce at an optimal cost. Our model is the following

$$p_{t+1} = p_t + \gamma F(e(\omega)N) + h_t \epsilon$$

Where p is the real price level, $e(w)$ is the effort of the labour force as a function of wage and F is the productivity. $\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$

Hypothesis: Let's consider that the marginal price is the same over two periods of time in which case we write:

$$\frac{dp_{t+1}}{dN} = \frac{dp_t}{dN}$$

Let's also suppose that the effort function is linear in which case we could write

$$e(w_1 + w_2) = e(w_1) + e(w_2)$$

We find that

$$\begin{aligned} E[w_t^* / \mathcal{F}] &= \frac{-1}{\gamma} E[\frac{dh_t}{dt} \epsilon] \\ &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

Where $w_t^* = \frac{dF(e(\omega_t)N)}{dN}$ is the marginal productivity, our model fits with the fact $E[w_t^* / \mathcal{F}] = 0$ which means that over the long time more employers won't ameliorate the productivity, which actually justifies the Keynesian assumption of involuntary unemployment

during business cycles, companies are reluctant to hire employees even with a lesser wage.

Conclusion: Under our model we had demonstrated that wages are foreseen to be sticky which more gives our research a different point of view, we used our model to price Vanilla Options using the bifractional brownian motion; in that road we would be using statistical considerations to dive into the economics of welfare.

We showed that wages set by the government can not obey to the heavy fist of the unions, there is somehow an equilibrium in that regard, the research question lies in defining how companies could encounter interest rate change besides the fact if unions are pushing for wages to be raised, that comes as no surprise. The power of companies lies in using their fist throughout the bond Market.

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